

CRITICAL THINKING SKILLS, FACILITIES AND METHOD OF TEACHING BASIC SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY FOR ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IN OYO WEST LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF OYO STATE**ADEGOKE Adebare Idowu Ph.D.***Department of Integrated Science**School of Secondary Education (Science Programmes)**Oyo State College of Education, Lanlate**08054041783**gokbare@gmail.com*

Abstract

This study investigated critical thinking skills, facilities and method of teaching Basic Science and Technology for economic development in Oyo West Local Government Area of Oyo State. Descriptive survey research design was used for the study. Population comprised all junior public secondary schools in Oyo West Local Government Area of Oyo State. Random Sampling was used to select ten (10) schools, 250 students (25 students from each of the schools) and 30 Basic Science and Technology teachers as sample for the study. Three instruments; questionnaires on Level of Critical Thinking Skills in Basic Science and Technology, Rating Scale and Facilities available for teaching Basic Science and Technology and Teacher Methods of Instruction with their reliability using Crombach alpha of 0.73, 0.75 and 0.77 respectively. The data collected were analyzed using mean, standard deviation and percentages. The findings revealed that the basic science students are low in critical thinking skills, there was the problem of inadequate facilities but the mode of instruction was teacher centered. It was recommended that students should employed critical thinking skills in their study; government should provide adequate instructional facilities for the teaching of Basic Science and Technology and teachers should embark on student-centered methods of instruction.

Keywords: Basic Science, Critical Thinking, Development, Skills Facilities and Teaching method

Introduction

Education is the most powerful instrument for social progress. Education remains one of the fundamental factors of development as it has the potential of enriching people's understanding of themselves and the world. It has the capacity to improve the quality of human life and it brings social benefits to individuals and society. Education has the potential to raise people's productivity and creativity and promote science and technological skills for advancement (Faruk, 2020).

The economic growth of a nation is determined by the increase in the capacity of its economy to produce goods and services for the comfort of the citizenry. This is why Omiko (2015) opined that the scientific,

technological, industrial and economic growth of any nation is strongly rooted in its quality of science education. Science and Technology is the cornerstone of the development of any nation. The linkages between science, technology, innovation and economic development are fairly well established. For example, a significant part of economic advancement has been attributed to improved productivity from technological innovation. Similarly, science education promotes creativity, innovation, productivity and economic growth (Zakariya & Bello, 2018). Education is an indispensable tool needed by everybody for their socio-economic development. In other words, socio-economic advancement of human beings in particular and the development of every society in

general depend on the quality of education being enjoyed. Hence, educational development becomes the major criterion for measuring overall national development otherwise known as improvement or change in growth. So, the development of any nation starts with the development of the individuals within the society. It is because the knowledge, skills, and competencies of human resources that determine, to a great extent, the level of wealth and development of a nation (Muhammed, Yusha'u & Lawal, (2018) and Isa & Usman (2021).

Science and Technology has been central in the progress and development of virtually all the nations of the world. It has contributed immensely to all section of the economy. Science and Technology are intimately connected with development because they have historical record of bringing advances that have led to healthier, longer, wealthier and more productive lives and they are key ingredients to solutions to the most serious economic development challenges that we currently face and likely to face in the future (Anaeto, et al (2016).

The planners of the curriculum for Basic Science advocate the provision of science equipment and materials (facilities) to help students understand scientific concepts. These science equipment and materials are expected to be used by teachers in a way that provides students with the opportunity to explore, observe and discuss scientific knowledge relating to their environment. One of the strategies being advocated for teaching and learning of Basic Science is the activity method (Ministry of Education, 2019). In this method, the student is at the core of the teaching and learning process and is made to actively interact with materials leading to making meaning of scientific concepts (Valentina & Kenneth 2002). To make science and technology creative and innovative according to Babayemi & Kareem, (2019), implies that Science and Technology should be taught in an environment that supports creativity and innovativeness. This environment, according to Adegoke (2023), consists of building, (classroom, and science laboratories technology, workshops, computer laboratory among others), the curriculum (creative, skill-inclined, process based) and the teacher (professionally

qualified, highly methodical, knowledgeable and skillful).

Critical thinking is that kind of thinking that can lead to meaningful result through creative ways of understanding and willingness to consider views where necessary. It has its basis from the National Policy on Education (FGN, 2014) which states that the major goal of education is to train and prepare people who will cultivate inquiry habit, acquire knowledge and rational minds for the conduct of a good life and produce scientists for national development. Some researchers such as Jittinum and Chakree (2003) and Regina, et al (2015) opined that people with critical thinking abilities are in high demand now and will continue to be relevant. It is a means of correct thinking in the pursuit of relevant and reliable knowledge about the world, and it is a reasonable, reflective, responsible and skillful thinking that is focused on deciding what to believe or not. It is also seen as higher order thinking and involves the formation of logical influence. Teachers can teach critical thinking by helping students to share their ideas, consider other students' perspectives, develop a sense of awareness, be responsive, and listen to others engaging in hand-on projects where students need to collaborate, communicate and analyze information and find solutions to their challenges.

Critical thinkers are inquisitive about a wide range of issues such as how things are, the way they are desire to become something in this global world, alert about opportunities, use critical thinking to solve global happenings, possess self-confidence in their own abilities to reason, open minded towards divergent world and making judgments (Facieme, 2010). Critical thinking skills help students to organized ideas and components of Basic Science and Technology concepts by searching for meaningful patterns of organizing information and putting things in groups. It is through critical thinking that students establish relationship between two or more ideas. When students acquire critical thinking skills on habits, they will have control over what they think and the areas they need to focus on in learning as well as managing their own learning.

The new Basic Science and Technology curriculum also call for

acquisition of basic knowledge and skills in science which is only achieved by exposing students to more of practical activities when teaching. This will make students to ask questions that will develop their thinking faculty. The Federal Government of Nigeria (FGN, 2014) also advocates for a great and dynamic economy. This goal can only be achieved when Science and Technology Students are taught to think critically and participate in activities that motivate them in acquiring and developing skills that make them to be self-reliant and in turn improve economic development of Nigeria.

Basic Science and Technology students need to think critically to help them in their thinking process, career choice and a qualitative way of life but is disheartening that they are not given the opportunity to involve in meaningful activity-based method can level of thinking.

Statement of the Problem

Critical thinking is a learned ability and must be taught through trained and knowledgeable teachers to impact the appropriate skills, but unfortunately many Nigerian Science and Technology teachers do not possess such but are dogmatic on the use of chalk and board methods (Adegoke 2015). This study, therefore, investigated critical thinking skills, facilities and method of teaching Basic Science and Technology for economic development in Oyo West Local Government Area of Oyo State.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to investigate critical thinking skills among Basic Science and Technology students for economic development in Oyo West Local Government Area of Oyo State. The study is specifically designed to:

- Determine the level of critical thinking skills among Basic Science and Technology students.
- Find out the availability of facilities for teaching of Basic Science and Technology that will develop students' critical thinking.

- Determine the qualification of teachers teaching Basic Science and Technology.
- Find out the method used by Basic Science and Technology teachers.

Research Questions

1. What is the level of Critical Thinking Skills of Basic Science and Technology students in Oyo West Local Government Area of Oyo State?
2. To what extents are facilities available for the teaching Basic Science and Technology to promote critical thinking?
3. What are the qualifications of teachers teaching Basic Science and Technology?
4. What are the teachers' methods of instruction in teaching Basic Science and Technology?

Methodology

This study adopted a descriptive survey research design and the population comprised all public junior secondary schools in Oyo West Local Government Area of Oyo State, random sampling technique was used to select 10 schools, 250 students (25 students from each of the schools using intact classes) and 30 Basic Science and Technology as sample for the study. Three questionnaires were used: questionnaires on Level of Critical thinking skills in Basic Science and Technology, Rating Scale and Facilities Available for Teaching Basic Science and Technology. The questionnaires were given to an expert in the Department of Integrated Science, Federal College of Education (Special) Oyo for validation.

The questionnaires were pilot tested and the result was used to calculate the reliability co-efficient using Crombach alpha and 0.73 and 0.79 was obtained respectively. The data were presented in tables and analyzed statistical tools such as, mean, standard deviation and percentages. The results obtained were used to answer the four research questions.

Results

Research question one: What is the level of students in Oyo West Local Government Area of Oyo State?

Table 1: Showing students responses on their critical thinking skills in Basic Science and Technology.

S/N	ITEM	X	S.D	DECISION
1	I'm always inquisitive on issues concerning basic science and technology.	2.40	1.29	Disagree
2	I have open-minded concerning people view relating to basic science and technology.	2.09	1.34	Disagree
3	I have confidence in my ability in basic science and technology.	2.84	1.60	Agree
4	I'm always alert to opportunities concerning critical thinking in basic science and technology.	2.56	1.53	Agree
5	Am not willing to tolerate changes in basic science and technology.	3.12	1.58	Agree
6	Am not flexible to people opinion in basic science and technology.	3.39	1.40	Agree

Table I reveals that the respondents disagreed on items 1 and 2. It can be said that basic science and technology students in the study area are low in critical thinking, since the respondents agree on items 3, 4, 5 & . However, items 5 and 6 were negative statements which indicated that the students were unwilling to change and were rigid to other people's option. They also disagreed being inquisitive on issues and being open minded concerning people's view. The table shows that they had confidence in their ability and are alert to opportunities. In conclusion, the table shows a low level of critical thinking because out of the six items they had agreement on only two items.

Research Question Two: What facilities are available for teaching Basic Science and Technology that will promote students critical thinking in Oyo Wet Local Government, Oyo State?

Table 2 showing students' responses on availability of facilities for the teaching Basic Science and Technology

S/N	ITEM	X	S.D	DECISION
1	Basic Science and Technology laboratory.	1.16	2.30	D
2	Standard Basic Science classroom.	3.50	1.42	A
3	A Basic Science and Technology workshop.	1.38	2.16	D
4	My Basic Science and Technology laboratory.	1.33	1.54	A
5	My school has equipment in Basic Science and Technology.	2.88	1.47	D

Table 2 shows that the respondents agreed on items 2 and 4 that the school has classrooms and no laboratory while items 3 and 4 disagreed that the schools have no laboratory technology.

Table 3: Showing teachers' responses on availability of facilities for teaching basic science and Technology.

S/N	ITEM	X	S.D	DECISION
1	Basic Science and Technology laboratory is in my school.	1.16	2.40	D
2	My school has a standard Basic Science classroom.	2.16	1.38	D
3	The school has a Basic Science and Technology workshop.	2.83	1.46	D
4	My Basic Science and Technology laboratory is not well equipped.	4.44	1.04	A
5	My school has qualified basic science and technology teachers	3.50	1.42	D

Table 3: Indicates that teachers disagreed on all items and agreed that there is no laboratory for Basic Science and Technology in their schools.

Research Question Three: What are the qualifications of the teachers teaching basic science and Technology in Oyo West Local Government of Oyo State?

Table 4 showing teachers responses on basic science and technology qualification for teaching the subject

S/N	QUALIFICATION	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
1.	NCE	15	50
2.	B.Sc. Ed.	10	33
3.	B.Sc with PGDE	2	7
4.	M. Sc. with PGDE	3	10
5.	Ph. D Science	-	-
	TOTAL	30	100

Table 4 shows that 50% of the teachers are NCE holders, 33% are B. Sc. Ed., B.Sc with PGDE are 7% while 10% have M.Sc. with PGDE

Table 5: showing teachers' responses on methods used by teachers in teaching Basic Science and Technology.

S/N	ITEMS	SA	A	UD	DA	SD
1.	Lecture method for easy coverage of syllabus	40(36%)	40(36%)	0(0%)	20(18%)	10(10%)
2.	Play way method	20(25%)	24(30%)	0(0%)	26(33%)	10(12%)
3.	Activity-based method	10(16%)	19(20%)	0(0%)	30(48%)	10(16%)
4.	Drama Method	10(16%)	44(54%)	0(0%)	20(25%)	7(9%)
5.	All items 1-4 methods	20(26%)	16(21%)	0(0%)	36(41%)	9(12%)

Table 5 shows that 36%, 36% and 0% strongly agreed, agreed and undecided in the usage of lecture for easy coverage of syllabus while 18% and 10% disagreed and strongly disagreed to the use of lecture. 25%, 30% and 0% strongly agreed, agreed and undecided in the use of play way method while 33% and 18% disagreed and strongly disagreed on the use of the method. 16%, 20% and 0% strongly agreed, agreed and undecided on the use of activity-based method while 48% and 16% indicated disagreed and strongly disagreed on the use of method respectively. In like manner, 12%, 54% & 0% strongly agreed, agreed and undecided on using drama method while 25% and 9% disagreed and strongly disagreed to the use of the method respectively. In the use of the four methods during Basic Science and technology teaching, 26%, 21% & 0% of the respondents strongly agreed, agreed and Undecided on their use, while 41% and 12% indicated disagreed and strongly disagreed to their combined use of the methods respectively.

Table 6: showing students' responses to teachers' methods of teaching Basic Science and Technology

S/N	ITEMS	SA	A	UD	DA	SD
1.	Lecture method for easy coverage of syllabus	50(33%)	60(36%)	0(0%)	30(18%)	10(7%)
2.	Play way method	40(27%)	50(30%)	0(0%)	40(33%)	20(13%)
3.	Activity-based method	20(13%)	10(20%)	0(0%)	50(48%)	70(47%)
4.	Drama method	10(7%)	20(54%)	0(0%)	80(53%)	49(33%)
5.	All items 1-4 methods are used	20(13%)	15(21%)	0(0%)	65(43%)	50(33%)

Table 7 results show 33%, 40% and 0% strongly agreed, agreed and undecided on the usage of lecture method while 20% and 7% disagreed and strongly disagreed on the use of the method. Furthermore, 27%, 33% and 0% strongly agreed, agreed and undecided showed the used of play way method while 27% and 13% were of opposite opinion. Besides, 13%, 10% and 0% indicated strongly agreed, agreed and undecided on the use of activity-based method while 33% and 47% disagreed and strongly disagreed respectively. This is not all, 7%, 14% and 6% strongly agreed, agreed and undecided indicated on the use of drama method while 53% and 33% disagreed and strongly

disagreed respectively. In addition, 13%, 10% and 0% strongly agreed, agreed and undecided that the four methods were used during Basic Science and Technology class while 43% and 33% disagreed and strongly disagreed respectively.

Discussions

Analysis of research question one showed that students' critical thinking skills in Basic Science and Technology in public schools in Oyo West Local Government was low as indicated by both students and teachers to have teaching innovative method and improve students' knowledge of understanding. This again would encourage the use of teacher-

centered activity than students-centered as there are no sufficient facilities to engage learners' activities in the learning process (Adegoke, 2014). It was also discovered that the students were unwilling to change and were rigid to other people' opinion and this might result in self-confidence on their parts. The result from students and teachers' responses showed activities-based method as the least method used among the four methods and indicated the lecture method as highest followed by drama and play way methods often used by teachers in teaching Basic Science and Technology and this is in line with Zakariyya and Bello and Aina, (2012) with views who explain that there would be no meaningful teaching and learning of Basic Science and Technology without adequate facilities, and an appropriate strategies that needed for the growth of the economy and the above in support of the findings of (Ibrahim,2022).

Conclusion

The study was carried out to investigate critical thinking skills among Basic Science and Technology teachers and students for economic development in Oyo West Local Government of Oyo State. It was discovered that most schools had no adequate facilities and lacked innovative methods. As such, the students lacked critical thinking skills in the learning of Basic Science and Technology. It is hoped that the availability of facilities such as well-structured classroom, equipment and qualified teachers enhance the learning of Basic Science and Technology for economic development in the area.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made:

1. Government should fund or provide schools with adequate facilities for the teaching and learning of Basic Science and Technology at all levels of education.
2. Teachers should facilitate the use of critical thinking skills to enhance positive attitude of students and improve their skills and achievement in Basic Science and Technology lesson.
3. Hard working Basic Science and Technology teachers should be given incentives to enable them work effectively.
4. Critical thinking skills should be employed by the students in learning Basic Science.

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